

METHODOLOGY FOR ESTIMATING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF A RESEARCH PROJECT IN THE FRAMEWORK OF RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION.

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a methodology for estimating the Carbon Footprint of a research project is presented. The methodology aims at helping research teams to foresee the impacts of their research on Global Warming. The methodology is intended for research fields in which energy intensity and Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHGE) are relevant but researchers are not tackling the problem yet.

The methodology aligns with the proposals of the European Union for RRI. In addition, it takes advantage of the existing tools for calculating the Carbon Footprint of products, services and processes like PAS 2050 and ISO 14064-II. Finally, it is tailored to the specificities of the research projects.

As a case study, it has been applied to a project aiming at developing proposals for promoting the logistics and connections of a Colombian region: Bolívar. The main GHG emissions are estimated to be due to the augment of road transportation and railway transportation of commodities, in the scenario of highest success. In the scenario of moderate success, the GHG emissions of executing the facilities are relevant and comparable with those of the goods transport. The GHG estimations ex-ante based in the methodology allowed introducing corrective measures for improving the environmental requirements of the research to be done.

Keywords: Carbon footprint, Sustainability, life cycle assessment, Responsible Research and Innovation, Climate Change.

1. Introduction

With the intention of fostering responsible research, the European Commission has been promoting a cross-cutting issue named “Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)”. A well known definition of RRI has been given by von

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Schomberg (2011): '(RRI) is a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products'.

The work by (Strand et al., 2015) suggested guidance to measure RRI. The measures should cover two dimensions of the research: "Performance", further divided into "Process" and "Outcomes"; and "Perception". It is actually a life cycle approach to estimating how responsible a research activity is. Moreover, Strand et al. include Sustainability among the consequences that should be addressed in RRI.

In a context of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), research teams should be willing to estimate ex-ante, and improve accordingly, the sustainability of their activities and outcomes. Besides, research policy makers are expected to start demanding sustainability estimations and corrective measures as a requisite for funding research.

In a previous publication by the authors (Ligardo-Herrera & Gómez-Navarro, 2017), a literature review and a network analysis was presented about the relationship between RRI and Environmental Sustainability, and Climate Change in particular. It was found several actors in Europe (and other regions) include Sustainability and or climate change in their research about RRI. Furthermore, several projects also included in their goals involving RRI in the sustainability pursuit and the global warming fight.

Based on that review, authors suggested four general recommendations for research and innovation practitioners to be responsible with regard to their contribution for climate change within RRI:

- i. Promote bottom-up voluntary engagement in RRI following the experience of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR);
- ii. Apply a life cycle perspective;
- iii. Develop and make available open source databases.
- iv. Minimize bureaucracy and the resources devoted to the ex-ante estimation

2. Literature Review

A new literature review was conducted with the specific target of publications and on going projects putting forward a tool for estimating the carbon footprint of a future research, or of an emerging technology. Despite finding that some authors are aware of the importance of adopting a RRI perspective, and mentioning

specifically consequences like fossil fuels depletion, climate change, and others (Burget, Bardone, & Pedaste, 2016; Pellé & Reber, 2016), no tool or methodology could be found.

The most similar publication was the paper by (Thorstensen & Forsberg, 2016) about Social Life Cycle Assessment as a resource for Responsible Research and Innovation. In that work, the authors prove the feasibility and utility of a methodology for ex-ante estimations of the impacts of a research project. Moreover, the authors identify the main difficulties such a methodology must overcome:

- i. Characterization of the research fields. The estimation of the carbon footprint (CF) should be done only in those research areas where Performance and Perception are related to high energy intensity and high GHG emissions. A taxonomy of the investigation fields should be done to distinguish when a research project is expected to have an impact on climate change.
- ii. Lack of data availability. For a life cycle assessment of the GHG emissions, and as a by-product the amount and type of energy consumption, different sets of data are needed and not always they can be directly measured, nor that is advisable. Data such as average GHG emissions, conversion factors, etc. must be readily available for quick and worthwhile CF estimates to be done.
- iii. Uncertainty about the research outcomes. It is normally difficult to foresee the diffusion and selling of Marketable products, if it is the case, or the assimilation of new knowledge and new procedures. Therefore, the impacts on market and society of the outcomes of the investigation can only be modelled by means of scenarios. On the other hand, wide intervals showing important differences among the best and worst possible results are expectable.

However, this ought not to be a problem since the estimation of the CF is more intended to distinguish the gaps in information, the hotspots for GHG emissions and to lead to put forward corrective measures, than to accurately calculate the CF of the research project.

3. Methodology

3.1 Objectives

The objective of the methodology is to estimate the greenhouse gases of the life cycle of a research project, emerging technology and, in general, any research and innovation activity.

3.2 Procedure

The methodology adapts the PAS 2050:2011, "Specification for the assessment of the life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of goods and services" (BSi, 2011); and the ISO 14064-II:2006, "Greenhouse gases - Part 2: Specification with guidance at the project level for quantification, monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emission reductions or removal enhancements" ("ISO 14064-2:2006, 2006). Besides, it adds other methods and tasks from other publications on carbon footprint, life cycle assessment (LCA) and RRI.

The methodology breaks the procedure into a series of stages and steps. These are sequential and cannot be carried out in isolation. Following the main stages and steps are presented:

Stage 1 – Scope

- Describe the project to be assessed and the functional unit
- Develop a model of the project life cycle
- Agree the 'system boundary' of the study
- Prioritize data collection activities

Stage 2 – Data collection

- Draw up a data collection plan
- Identify and engage stakeholders
- Collect secondary emission factors and other secondary data to fill in the gaps
- Check the data and assess data quality

Stage 3 – Footprint calculations

- Compile activity data and balance flows according to the functional unit
- Multiply activity data by emission factors to generate the footprint
- Check calculations and record all data sources and assumptions

Stage 4 – interpreting footprint results and driving reductions

- Identify hotspots
- Test sensitivity
- Identify reduction opportunities
- Ensure transparency where communicating

4. Case Study

To test the feasibility and utility of the methodology it was applied to a case study: the project “Research and Innovation in Logistics and Ports” developed by a team in the Universidad Tecnológica de Bolívar. The goal of the project is to design a proposal for the improvement of the transport connections and logistics of a Colombian region. The region has a great commercial potential for agro products (especially cocoa and oil palm). This project represent one of the components of a macro project named “Logport” for the regions of “Montes de María” and “Magdalena Medio”.

The project will have to choose among alternatives like improving the existing infrastructure, investing in new infrastructure, and an alternative combining improving the existing infrastructure and executing new ones. Moreover, all strategies could be further broken down into different options based on different transport means, different ownership of the facilities, different designs on the map, different ICT protagonism, different introduction schedules, etc.

The project will be solved designing and implementing models of strategic planning and operation in the agro industrial supply chain of the department of Bolívar, using quantitative mathematical analysis and simulation techniques. From the beginning, based on the requirements of the public funding call for projects, the carbon footprint of the project is not required. Indeed, only socio-economic requirements were published. However, the research team wanted to assess the CF of the project. Partly due to its responsibility and partly to make its proposal more competitive. For that, they considered not only the research process, but its outcomes in case the project's proposals were finally carried out in the Bolívar region.

5. Findings and conclusions

The methodology could be applied without an excessive consumption of resources: time, money, etc. Although there were several estimations that did not fully satisfied the research team because they were too uncertain. Based on the methodology up to 24 different scenarios were designed in a first review. Those scenarios were merged in 6 final main possible scenarios for the outcomes of the project. In none of them, the research process had a relevant contribution to the carbon footprint of the project.

The main were modelled based on the alternative transport facilities and the size of the future development of the agro products production and its transportation.

They were named “mainly railway best, worst and average scenarios” and “mainly road transport best, worst and average scenarios”.

Although the estimations were very uncertain, ranging from a few thousand tons of equivalent Carbon Dioxide (tCO_{2e}) to several hundred million tCO_{2e} in 10 years, the methodology allowed identifying the GHG hotspots, the main information gaps and the potential measures to mitigate or prevent the carbon footprint.

The main GHG hotspots of the research project would be:

- The execution of the infrastructure
- The energy consumption of the industrialization of agro products
- The energy consumption of the transport means

The main information gaps could be:

- The energy consumed by the agro industries in the different scenarios.
- The end of life of the waste of the agro industry in the scenarios of higher success.
- The energy mix for the transportation infrastructure

The main proposals for improvement could be:

- To promote railroad transport as much as possible
- To promote renewable sources of energy for agro industries. Mainly based on organic waste for preventing it from being disposed in landfills.
- To promote renewable energy sources for the electricity of the railroad system.

Besides, it was proven than anticipatory carbon footprint measuring is not about calculating accurately, but rather systematically and iteratively explores uncertainties across the life cycle of a research project. The real aim is prioritize research alternatives with the greatest potential for environmental improvement. That way it contributes to responsible innovation by redirecting a technology's development pathway.

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